

Investigating Place Reputation using Place-based Subreddits and Geospatial Knowledge Graphs

Extended abstract of the COSIT 2024 doctoral mentorship program

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My PhD research proposes to construct a geospatial knowledge graph (GeoKG) from unstructured social media place descriptions to represent ‘patial information’. Knowledge graphs have rarely been applied to the study of place, despite their advantages over traditional geospatial data models. Moreover, unstructured social media data has been challenging to formalise in GeoKG models due to its noisiness and heterogeneous spatial knowledge. As a result, a huge amount of patial information that represent ‘informal’ views on place, remains obscured from formal computational representation.

A patial knowledge graph will be built from Reddit, an under-utilised social media platform in geographic research but a potential repository of patial information through its place-based subreddits (e.g. r/Leeds). A schema layer will be defined, which models the domain knowledge to formalise entities and relations found from unstructured social media data. A data layer will also be defined, utilising advanced natural language processing techniques to extract knowledge from unstructured social media data, including named-entity recognition, spatial relation extraction and toponym resolution. Particular attention will be drawn to the capabilities of large language models (LLMs) in their capabilities for spatial relation extraction.

Reddit place descriptions will be modelled and represented in a knowledge graph, to measure and analyse place reputation. Understanding the reputation of places has implications for belonging, health and wellbeing, however, is relatively understudied in finer geographical scales. In addition, previous measures struggle to capture lived experience. The variation in reputations for different places within an urban environment will be explored, along with identifying what aspects of place define its reputation. It is hypothesised that an urban hierarchy may form, where different places within an urban environment are ranked through collective agreement. The knowledge graph created has potential to be implemented into a GeoAI model, to predict place reputations of unknown places.

From the beginning of my 2nd year, there have been some preliminary results in constructing the GeoKG. In terms of the schema layer, a KG database model has been specified, which formalises relationships between actual geographic entities and ‘patial concepts’. In terms of the data layer, the capabilities of LLMs have been tested in named entity recognition and spatial relation extraction for Reddit text data. Preliminary experiments have shown some promising results. A small scale patial-knowledge graph has been constructed and is hosted on Neo4j, representing patial information within Leeds, UK.